

Linked data is meaningful knowledge

Brief use case for linked data in life sciences

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Some terminology

- **Semantic web**

"The Semantic Web is an extension of the current web in which **information is given well-defined meaning**, better enabling computers and people to work in cooperation." (Berners-Lee et al.)

- **Linked data**

A set of best practices for publishing structured data on the web, using hyperlinks to connect resources through **unique identifiers** and the Resource Description Framework.

- **Ontologies and controlled vocabularies**

Berners-Lee, T., Hendler, J., & Lassila, O. (2001). The Semantic Web. A New Form of Web Content That Is Meaningful to Computers Will Unleash a Revolution of New Possibilities. *Scientific American*, 284, 1-5.

Ontologies and controlled vocabularies are the backbone of linked data

Food Ontology

Keywords: Search terms

Class: croissant

Term IRI: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03309852

Annotations

- **database_cross_reference:**<https://bioregistry.io/reference/siren:F9852>
- **has_curation_status:**requires discussion
- **http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#comment:**SIREN DB annotation: * has quality 'whole, shape achieved by forming, thickness 1.5-7 cm.' (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03430105) * has quality 'fully heat-treated' (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03440014) * derives from 'seed, skin removed, germ removed (endosperm)' (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03420208) * formed as a result of 'food baking process' (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03450005) * formed as a result of 'carbohydrate fermentation process' (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03460256) * has substance added http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03460184 * has substance added "butter added" (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FOODON_03460271)
- **imported from:**<http://langual.org>

Unlinked data

Sample scenario

We are trying to estimate the dietary energy intake from two food intake surveys for posterior comparison and analyses:

- One for school kids in the Netherlands,
- Another one for school kids in Nigeria

We'll need to use the adequate food composition tables for each country.

Unlinked data

multiple hits for the text search: croissant

1. Finding the Excel Spreadsheets or PDFs
 - The Dutch Food Composition data (NEVO)

	C	D	E	F	G	L	croissan	9 de 17	^	v	:	x
1	Food group	NEVO-code	Voedingsmiddelnaam/Dutch f	Engelse naam/Food name	Synoniem	ENERCJ (kJ)	ENERCC (kcal)	WATE				
116	Bread	2799	Broodje meergranen- hard	Roll multigrain hard	Pistolet meergr	1238	294					
117	Bread	2800	Broodje meergranen- zacht	Roll multigrain soft	Meergranenbo	1189	283					
118	Bread	2801	Croissant roomboter-	Croissant prepared w butter		1729	414					
119	Bread	2802	Croissant z roomboter	Croissant prepared wo butter		1639	392					
120	Bread	2803	Bol krenten-	Bun currant/raisin	Krentenbol/roz	1134	268					
121	Bread	2804	Bol muesli- meel/volkorenmeel	Bun brown/wholemeal w	Mueslibol	1221	290					
122	Bread	2811	Brood volkoren- fijn	Bread wholemeal fine	Volkorenbrood	985	233					
123	Bread	2812	Brood krenten/rozijnen m spij	Bread current/raisin w alr	Krentenbrood r	1277	303					
124	Bread	2813	Brood rozijnen-krenten gem	Bread raisin/current av	Krentenbrood r	1153	272					
125	Bread	2814	Brood rozijnen- m spijs	Bread raisin w almond pa	Rozijnenbrood	1276	303					
126	Bread	2815	Brood tijger- bruin	Bread Tijger brown wheat	Bruinbrood tijg	1019	241					
127	Bread	2816	Brood tijger- wit	Bread Tijger white	Witbrood tijger	1062	251					
128	Bread	2817	Stol m spijs gem m en z noten	Stollen w almond/imitat f	Kerststol/paass	1191	282					
129	Bread	2818	Croissant gem	Croissant av		1684	403					
130	Bread	2821	Brood tarwe- m pompoenpitte	Bread brown w pumpkin	Bruinbrood tar	1164	277					
131	Bread	2830	Croissant kaas-	Croissant cheese	Kaascroissant	1673	400					
132	Bread	2876	Brood brioche	Bread brioche		1422	338					
133	Bread	2916	Cracker VitaLU verrijkt m calci	Cracker VitaLU w added c	Vitalu cracker n	1764	419					

NEVO-online
versie 2019/6.0,
RIVM, Bilthoven

Unlinked data

one hit for the text search: croissant

- Finding the Excel Spreadsheets or PDFs
 - The West African Food Composition Tables from the FAO

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Code	Food name in English	Food name in French	Scientific name	BibliolD/Source	Edible portion coefficient 1 (from as purchased to as described)	Energy (kJ)	Energy (kcal)	Water (g)
2	Code	Nom d'aliment en anglais	Nom d'aliment en français	Nom scientifique	BibliolD/Source	Portion comestible 1 (rapport entre l'aliment décrit et l'aliment acheté)	Énergie (kJ)	Énergie (kcal)	Eau (g)
3						EDIBLE1	ENERC	ENERC	WATER
15	01_160	Cantonese rice with fish and noodles (Burkina Faso)*	Riz cantonnais avec poisson et vermicelles (Burkina Faso)*		calc. from recipe / de recette		1080	259	
16	01_182	Cornflakes (breakfast cereal), unfortified	Cornflakes (céréales pour petit-déjeuner), non enrichis		AU14(02D10351)	1.00	1620	383	
17	01_189	Croissant, plain, unfortified	Croissant, nature, non enrichi		AU14(02E40103), SA10(3413), UK7(11-988)	1.00	1560	373	
18	01_002	Fonio, black, whole grains, raw	Fonio, noir, grains entiers, cru	<i>Digitaria iburua</i>	1M(12), FAO(1), IN17(A010; A003; A016; A017), KEN18(001025), US28(20031), 01_001	1.00	1400	332	
19	01_124	Fonio, black, whole grains, boiled* (as part of a recipe)	Fonio, noir, grains entiers, bouilli* (ingrédient de recette)	<i>Digitaria iburua</i>	calc. from / de 01_002	1.00	583	138	
20	01_049	Fonio, black, whole grains, boiled* (without salt), drained	Fonio, noir, grains entiers, bouilli* (sans sel), égoutté	<i>Digitaria iburua</i>	calc. from / de 01_002	1.00	583	138	
					1M(367), 6N, BF1044, FAO(4), IN17(A010; A003; A016; A017)				

Stadlmayr, B. (2012). West African food composition table/table de composition des aliments d'Afrique de l'Ouest.

Unlinked data

1. Finding the Excel Spreadsheets or PDFs
2. Are these the same things?
 - Need to dive into the supporting documentation and literature to check

17	01_189	unfortified	petit-déjeuner), non enrichis	AU14(02E40103), SA10(3413), UK7(11-988) 1M(12). FAO(11.	1.00	1560	373
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Bread	2801	Croissant roomboter-	Croissant prepared w butter	1729	414
Bread	2802	Croissant z roomboter	Croissant prepared wo butter	1639	392

No, they are not the same, but...

They are all subclasses of “croissant”

Linked data (ideal scenario)

What is the energy content of a croissant in kilojoules, according to the Dutch Food Composition table?

And for the West African Food Composition table?

How does this "croissant" entry compare to a standard "croissant" term?

Researcher

query through a
user-friendly
interface

Food composition
semantic knowledge
base

output

?source	?label	?kJ	?compare_croissant
West African Food Composition Table (FAO)	Croissant, plain, unfortified		sameAs
NEVO	Croissants canned baked		narrower
NEVO	Croissant roomboter		sameAs

Linked data limitations as of today


```
PREFIX rdf:
<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX rdfs:
<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
PREFIX ex: <https://example.com/>
PREFIX foodon: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/foodon#>
```

```
SELECT ?source ?label ?energyContent
?compare_croissant
WHERE {
{
ex:DutchFoodCompositionTable ex:containsFoodItem
?croissant.
?croissant ex:hasEnergyContent ?energyContent.
?energyContent rdf:type ex:Kilojoules.
?croissant rdf:type foodon:croissant. (...)
.....
```


output

?source	?label	?kJ	?compare_croissant
West African Food Composition Table (FAO)	Croissant, plain, unfortified	1900	sameAs
NEVO	Croissants canned baked	2000	narrower
NEVO	Croissant roomboter	2300	sameAs

Food composition semantic knowledge base with its own schema

What can you do as a data producer?

The development of ontologies and knowledge bases could be significantly sped up if data producers...

- Read on the FAIR principles and try to make your data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
 - Publicly release your data and add metadata (if possible)
- Use apps like the **Ontology Lookup Service** or **OntoBee** to find ontology terms to make your datasets informative and easy to wrangle